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EPIDEMIOLOGY STUDIES OF MUCOPOLYSACCHARIDOSES LYSOSOMAL DISEASES IN THE POPULATION OF AZERBAIJAN REPUBLIC

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ABSTRACT

The first time we started our epidemiological studies of mucopolysaccharidoses lysosomal diseases in the population of Azerbaijan Republic. Each suspicious patient in mucopolysaccharidoses lysosomal diseases underwent medical genetic consultation, glucosaminoglycans were analysed in the urine with thin-layer chromatography, relative lysosomal enzyme activities were analyzed in blood serum. Gene level diagnostics were done by means of Sanger sequencing and New Generation Sequencing genetic methodiques. Altogether there 947 genetically affected patients and their family members from 29 out of 86 economic regions of the country.

Mucopolysaccharidosis affected 34 patients (homozygotes) and 89 heterozygotes were identified. Patients were checked up for all five types of mucopolysaccharidoses: Hurler (MPS I), Hunter (MPS II), Sanfilippo (MPS III), Morquio (MPS IV), Maroteaux-Lamy (MPS VI). Phenotypic and gene frequencies of mucopolysaccharidoses were counted. The lowest frequency was evaluated for Hurler syndrome (5,9%), then came Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome (7,7%). The highest frequency among all identified MPS syndromes - around half of them (50%) - was for Morquio syndrome. MPS IVA/MPS IVB ratio was 16:1. Hurler and Sanfilippo syndromes had frequencies as high as 14,7% and 20,6%. The Republic population mucopolysaccharidoses phenotypic frequencies were presented with comparison to populations of countries and continents.

Based on the obtained practical and scientific results the ways for prophylaxis would be developed, designed and implemented for families with genetic risk of mucopolysaccharidoses.

Keywords: Hunter, Hurler, Maroteaux-Lamy, Morquio, Mucopolysaccharidoses, Sanfilippo.

Introduction. Mucopolysaccharidosis (MPS) being a disease of the connective tissue, it is a metabolic disorder as a result of acidic glucosaminoglycans (GAG-mucopolysaccharides) enzyme deficit. Disease being inherited, having features of lysosome storage diseases' group turns to be reasons for pathologic changes in bones, cartilages and connective tissues. Around 25% of lysosomal metabolic diseases are registered as MPS's. [9.p.11-18].

The following MPS types and their clinic manifestations, biochemistry and genetics were studied: MPS I type (Hurler syndrome, Hurler/Scheie syndrome, Scheie syndrome), MPS II type (Hunter syndrome), MPS III type (Sanfilippo A, Sanfilippo B, Sanfilippo C, Sanfilippo D), MPS IV type (Morquio syndrome A, Morquio syndrome B), MPS VI type (Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome), MPS VII type - (Sly syndrome - beta-glucuronidase enzyme deficiency), MPS IX syndrome [18, p.78-95; 27, p.23-29].

The following contemporary classification is presented depending upon enzyme deficiency peculiarities. Three phenotypes of Hurler syndrome were identified: Hurler syndrome, Scheie syndrome and Hurler/Scheie syndrome. Hurler syndrome (MPS IH), Scheie syndrome (MPS ISch), Hurler/Scheie syndrome

(MPS IHSch).The disease causes IDUA gene activity damage which leads to the deficiency of Iduronat-2-sulfatase. IDUA gene is located in autosome Xromosome 4 in 16.3 locus (4p16.3). This gene is registered under 607014, 607015 and 607016 numbers in OMIM classification [5, p.65-70; 13, p.30; 22, p.233-239].

The goal of the paper was epidemiologic (populational) studies of Mucopolysaccharidosis lysosomal storage diseases in Azerbaijan Republic. For that purpose patients suspicious with Mucopolysaccharidoses were genetically consulted, tested for glucosaminoglycans in their urine, lysosomal enzymes' activities were evaluated in blood serum and genetic tests on DNA level were done.

Material and methods. Material was collected during 2018-2024 years in Azerbaijan Republic, namely in Guba-Khachmas, Lankaran-Astara, Sheki-Zagatala, Western Zangazur economic regions and Baku and Gyandza cities in children's clinics by means of GENOM clinic laboratory and MedOlimp clinic when carrying genetic consultations with families.

Altogether 947 children with inherited diseases and their family members were identified. There were 34 patients with MPS lysosomal storage homozygotes

and double heterozygotes, and 89 heterozygotes identified.

Quantitative and qualitative analysis of GAG's in urine were carried out with thin layer chromatography methodique for suspicious with lysosomal storage patients. Mass spectrometry method was applied for blood serum lysosomal enzyme analyses. Family trees were created, and blood relation types and their structure were studied [23, p.2700-2711].

DNA analysis was used to confirm suspicious clinic manifestations. Genetic study conducted with NGS (Next Generation Sequencing) technique. To isolate DNA, QIAamp DNA Blood mini kit (Germany manufactured) was used. Analysis was carried out on the panel designed MiSeq Illumina apparatus manufactured by Illumina® (USA). Panel included the following genes: GALNS, IDUA, IDS, GALC, SUMF1, GAA, GUSB, GBA1, GLB1, ARSB, PAH, SMPD1, ADGRV1 and PLA2G6. Sequencing of GALNS, IDUA, IDS, GBA1 genes on DNA level was identified with NGS technique (Next Generation Sequencing). There were used the following kits and programmes: kit - Lysosomal Storage Disease Kit, Celeomics®; Analysis Platform - MiSeq Sequencing, Illumina®; Analysis programme - SEQ analysis platform, GENOMIZE® (<http://seq.genomize.com>), GRCh37(h19) [3, p. 28-36].

“DNA samples with their gene mutations were identified on that panel with Next Generation Sequencing technique. More than 99% gene coding sites were studied with reading depth of not less than 50X. Mean reading depth was 1559 indications. Analysis included exon-intron linkage (± 10 np).” The pathogeny classification of the obtained results was conducted according to “Guidelines of ACMG®”.

Results and discussion. Populational studies of Mucopolysaccharidoses lysosome storage diseases started in 2018 in children's hospitals and clinics of Absheron economic region, Baku and Gyandza cities for Azerbaijan Republic population. In that studies GENOM clinic laboratory and MedOlimp clinic took part for medical genetic consultancy and lab tests. Doctor geneticist and doctor pediatrician were participating in Central Regional Hospitals during those examinations and consultancies. Prior to meetings with patients lectures were conducted, clinical data and general information about MPS lysosomal storage diseases were presented to doctors in those hospitals. Doctors in hospitals and health centers after lectures and having learnt from clinical documents started to differentiate those affected children examining MPS-like children, arranging their genetic consultations in presence of doctor geneticist and doctor pediatrician with further biochemical and genetic tests.

There were identified 78 patients from Guba-Khachmas economic region incorporated Guba, Khachmaz, Shabran, Gusar and Siyazan regions, 112 patients from Sheki-Zagatala economic areas including Sheki, Balakan, Gakh, Zagatala, Oghuz and Gabala regions, 63 patients from Lankaran-Astara economic region including Masalli, Astara, Lankaran, Lerik, Jalilabad and Yardymly regions, the biggest economic region of the country 119 patients from Merkezi Aran

economic region consisted of Agdash, Goychay, Kyurdamir, Ujar, Yevlakh, Zardab regions and Mingechevir city, 92 patients from Garabagh economic region including Aghjabedi, Aghdam, Agdash, Barda, Khojaly, Shusha, Fyuzuli, Tartar regions and Khankendi city, 28 patients from Western Zangazur economic region incorporating Kalbajar, Gubadly, Zangilan, Lachin and Jabrayil regions, 43 patients from Mountaineous Shirvan economic region including Aghsu, Ismayilly, Gobustan and Shamakhy, 32 patients from Nakhchivan economic region, 57 patients from Mil-Mughan economic region involving Beylagan, Imishli, Saatly, Sabirabad regions, 28 patients from Gazakh-Tovuz economic region comprising of Tovuz, Gazakh, Aghstafa, Gadabay and Shamkir regions, 41 patients from Shirvan-Salyan economic region Shirvan, Salyan, Bilasivar, Hajigabul and Neftchala regions, 48 patients from Absheron economic region.

Altogether 947 patients were consulted on genetics, results of those consultations were mainly carried out for mucopolysaccharidoses suspicious patients after their tests for urine GAG chromatography analyses, relative enzymes' activities evaluation in the Republic. To carry out tests to identify Mucopolysaccharidoses syndrome types on the DNA molecule level, blood lymphocytes were separated.

So, 947 persons - affected children and their family members underwent medical genetic consultancy, and necessary biochemical and genetic analyses were carried out based on the MPS clinics. 31 patients, their parents and siblings were tested according to their primary suspicious MPS diagnosis. Three siblings revealed clinic manifestations of Hunter (MPS II), Sanfilippo (MPS III) and Morquio (MPS IV) syndromes.

Diagnosis based on clinical manifestations 34 suspicious patients to be confirmed first of all GAG in urine was analysed qualitatively and quantitatively with thin layer chromatography methodique. Identified dextran sulfate (DS) and heparan sulfate (HS) quantities in seven samples were higher than norm DS-25,31-44,5% (N-14,74%), HS-50,33-52,06% (N-29,32%). Higher values of DS and HS in urine tells us about two MPS types: MPS I (Hurler Syndrome) and MPS II (Hunter Syndrome). To differentiate these two types from one another, enzyme analysis was used. In five samples out of seven total and residue activity deficits of iduronat-2-sulfatase (IDS) (0 mmol/L/h - 0,8 μ mol/L/h \geq 5,6 μ mol/L/h) was found. IDS enzyme deficit corresponds with Hunter syndrome. Two patients showed “0” activity of Iduronate-2-sulfatase (IDUA) enzyme (N- >1,5 mmol/h). And that was biochemical confirmation of Hurler syndrome. Eleven and more heterozygotes were identified in their family members during testing.

Urine analysis of seven patients revealed high value of heparan sulfate (HS). High values of HS in urine indicated MPS III syndrome presence. For four (A, B, C, and D) types of the Syndrome four different specific to types enzyme activities were analysed. These enzymes were as followed: Iduronat-2-sulfatase enzyme corresponded to Sanfilippo A, N-acetyl-alfa-glucosaminidase (NAGLU) enzyme - to Sanfilippo B, Heparan-alfa-glucosaminidase N-acetyltransferase (HGSNAT) enzyme - to Sanfilippo C and characteristic

to Sanfilippo D type syndrome was N-acetylglucosamine-6-sulfatase (GNS) enzyme. Based on the results of the test, three of tested patients revealed Sanfilippo syndrome Type A, two - Sanfilippo syndrome Type B, and the rest two had got Sanfilippo syndrome Type C. Majority of patients - seventeen of them identified high values of keratan sulfate (KS) and chondroitin sulfate (ChS) in their urine tests, that confirmed their Morquio syndrome Types A and B (MPS IVA, MPS IVB). Blood test identified 16 patients galactosamine-6-sulfatase (GALNS) enzyme deficiency (0,0-1,3 mmol/L/h- $\geq 2,0 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$) that described Morquio syndrome Type A. And only one patient had enzyme test result ($0 \mu\text{mol/L/h N} \geq 8,8 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$) specific to Morquio syndrome Type B (MPS IVB).

Three patients had got high values of only DS enzyme tested in urine. Arylsulfatase beta (ARSB) total

and residue deficiency ($0-0,3 \mu\text{mol/L/h N} >1,0 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$) showed Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome (MPS VI).

Hence, taking into account clinic features that were likely the same as of MPS lysosomal storage diseases, after biochemically analysing urine and blood samples of 34 patients, two patients were identified as Hurler syndrome (MPS I), five of them Hunter syndrome (MPS II), seven Sanfilippo syndrome (MPS III) types A, B and C, sixteen had got Morquio syndrome type A (MPS IVA), one Morquio syndrome type B (MPS IVB), three patients were with Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome (MPS VI). Found number of MPS lysosome storage syndromed patients and their types, results of urine and blood tests, pathogenic genes' phenotypic and gene frequencies of the diseases are presented in the Table 1.

Table 1.

MPS patient number, types, urine and blood test results, phenotypic and gene frequencies

Number of patients	Urine analysis	Results of blood enzyme analysis	MPS types	Phenotypic and gene frequencies
2	DS HS	IDUA "0" activity (N - $>1,5\text{mmol/h}$)	MPS I Hurler Syndrome	5,88% 0,0635
5	DS HS	IDS 0 mmol/L/h - $0,8 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ $N \geq 5,6 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$	MPS II Hunter Syndrome	14,71% 0,0794
7	HS 1	SGSH 0 - $0,6 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ $N \geq 1,0 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ NAGLU 0 - $0,2 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ $N \geq 2,0 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ HGSNAT 0 - $0,8 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ $N \geq 3,5 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$	MPS IIIA MPS IIIB MPS IIIC Sanfilippo Syndrome	20,59% 0,2698
16	KS CS	GALNS 0 - $0,7 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ $N \geq 2,0 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ GLB1 0,1 $\mu\text{mol/L/h}$ $N \geq 2,8 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$	MPS IVA MPS IVB Morquio Syndrome	50,0% 0,2698
1				
3	DS	ARSB 0 - $0,3 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$ $N >1,0 \mu\text{mol/L/h}$	MPS VI Maroteaux-Lamy Syndrome	8,8% 0,0376

Hurler syndrome (MPS I) was revealed in two patients from Aghdam region and one from Barda region. Additionally four persons showed to be heterozygous carriers of IDUA gene. Hurler syndrome phenotypic and gene frequencies in Aghdam and Barda regions were as $5 \cdot 10^4$, $2 \cdot 10^4$ and $7 \cdot 10^4$, $3 \cdot 10^5$ relatively. One patient in Zangilan region was identified as a heterozygous carrier of IDS.

One patient from Mashtagha settlement in Absheron region was identified as affected homozygote with Hunter syndrome (MPS II). Phenotypic and IDS gene frequencies on the Mashtagha settlement were $23 \cdot 10^4$ and $9 \cdot 10^5$. Totally, phenotypic and IDS gene

frequencies throughout Absheron region were distributed as followed: 2,29%, 0,0229 and 0,20%, 0,0020 respectively. Because of X-linked inheritance of Hunter syndrome, only his mother was a carrier of IDS gene. Genetic examination showed that except patient's mother, a sibling (sister) had got the same heterozygosity ($2 \cdot 10^4$, $1 \cdot 10^5$).

Hurler syndrome was found in Gazakh region (1 hemizygote, three heterozygotes), in Shamakhy (two hemizygotes, five heterozygotes) and in Ujar region (one hemizygote, three heterozygotes). Phenotypic and gene frequencies are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Results of MPS epidemiological studies in Azerbaijan Republic population

Region name	Residents	MPS type	Index patient number	Number of heterozygotes	Phenotypic frequency (%)	Gene frequency (in fraction)
Mashtagha Absheron	43,700 491,316	MPS II	1	3	$44 \cdot 10^4$	$9 \cdot 10^5$
Aghjabadi	135,500	MPS IV	1	3	$7 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Aghdash	88,379	MPS IV	1	4	$113 \cdot 10^5$	$3 \cdot 10^4$
Aghstafa	88,379	MPS III	1	2	$113 \cdot 10^5$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Aghdam	202,200	MPS I	1	2	$5 \cdot 10^4$	$3 \cdot 10^5$
		MPS III	1	3	$5 \cdot 10^4$	$1 \cdot 10^5$
		MPS:II	1		$113 \cdot 10^5$	$5 \cdot 10^6$
Beylagan	91,000	MPS V	1	3	$11 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Barda	143,900	MPS I	1	2	$7 \cdot 10^4$	$3 \cdot 10^5$
Bilyasuvar	231,800	MPS VI	1	4	$4 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Dashkesan	34,476	MPS III	1	2	$29 \cdot 10^4$	$5 \cdot 10^5$
Guba	47,000	MPS IV	1	3	$21 \cdot 10^4$	$5 \cdot 10^5$
Gyoranboy	119,400	MPS IV	1	2	$8 \cdot 10^4$	$17 \cdot 10^6$
Gyoychay	119,400	MPS IV	1	4	$84 \cdot 10^5$	$25 \cdot 10^6$
Goygyol	60,890	MPS IV	1	3	$16 \cdot 10^4$	$37 \cdot 10^5$
Hajigabul	77,027	MPS IV	1	2	$130 \cdot 10^5$	$4 \cdot 10^4$
Khachmas	178,100	MPS VI	1	4	$6 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Khyzy	17,075	MPS III	2	4	$117 \cdot 10^4$	$23 \cdot 10^5$
Ismayilly	87,867	MPS IV	1	2	$11 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Kyurdamir	117,923	MPS IV	1	2	$8 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
		MPS VI	1	3	$8 \cdot 10^5$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Gazakh	103,994	MPS II	1	3	$10 \cdot 10^4$	$4 \cdot 10^5$
Lachin	80,163	MPS III	1	4	$12 \cdot 10^4$	$4 \cdot 10^5$
Saatly	107,800	MPS IV	1	2	$9 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Sabirabad	180,458	MPS IV	1	2	$6 \cdot 10^4$	$1 \cdot 10^5$
Siyazan	43,604	MPS IV	3	8	$69 \cdot 10^4$	$16 \cdot 10^5$
Shamakhy	105,100	MPS II	2	5	$19 \cdot 10^4$	$5 \cdot 10^5$
Sheki	187,031	MPS III	1	2	$5 \cdot 10^4$	$1 \cdot 10^5$
		MPS IV	1	2	$5 \cdot 10^4$	$1 \cdot 10^5$
Ujar	88,600	MPS II	1	3	$11 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Zagatala	126,900	MPS IV	1	2	$8 \cdot 10^4$	$2 \cdot 10^5$
Zangilan	44,800	MPS III		1		$1 \cdot 10^5$

Sanfilippo syndrome (MPS III) was identified in seven patients. Creation of family tree during consultation and biochemical/genetic analyses revealed seventeen heterozygotes on the syndrome. MPS III syndrome patients were residents of Aghstafa, Aghdam, Dashkesan, Khyzy, Lachin and Sheki regions. The highest genotypic frequency was in Khyzy region ($7 \cdot 10^4$), and the lowest - in Aghdam and Sheki regions ($5 \cdot 10^4$).

Morquio syndrome (MPS IV) was revealed in 17 regions of the Republic. High frequency was found in Siyazan region residents. Three unrelated individuals were identified as patients with Morquio syndrome in Siyazan within population 43604 residents. Phenotypic and gene frequencies of the syndrome in this region was evaluated as $69 \cdot 10^4\%$, $16 \cdot 10^5$. The lowest frequency of Morquio syndrome ($2 \cdot 10^5$) was registered in Sheki, Sabirabad and Guba regions' inhabitants.

Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome (MPS VI) three patients from three regions: Beylagan, Bilyasuvar and Khachmas were identified. Phenotypic and gene frequencies distributed as shown: Beylagan - $11 \cdot 10^4$, $2 \cdot 10^5$; Bilyasuvar - $4 \cdot 10^4$ $2 \cdot 10^5$ and Khachmas - $6 \cdot 10^4$, $2 \cdot 10^5$, relatively.

During parents questioning it happened that 26 (83,9%) parent marriage pairs in 31 families of index patients turned to be conanguine relatives. And 21 of those marriages were cousin (second degree) marriages that comprised 80,8%. Consanguineous cousin (third degree) and endemic marriages was evaluated as 19,2%.

Now let us compare world data on MPS's and our results found in Azerbaijan Republic. More than 60 years has an experience of European populational geneticists who work with MPS's and during that period more than 4000 patients were identified. MPS I consisted 19,72% [6, p.1011-1017; 8, p.273; 13, p.108; 14, p.194-195; 16, p.205-210; 17, p.227-240; 19, p.389-390]. Average frequency of MPS I in Asian continent among all MPS types was 23,5%. The highest frequency - 83,1% was in Pakistan, the lowest - 6,0% in Taiwan population [17, p.227-240; 25, p.231]. Average MPS's frequencies on American continent was 25,31%. Where the highest frequency was 30,0% in British Columbia province of Canada, and the lowest - 9,5% in Columbia population. In Asian continent Hurler syndrome frequencies were 21,0% and 25% for Saudi Arabia and Tunisia, respectively, with average

value of 23,0% [11, p.345-349; 20, p.271]. In Australia frequency for MPS's was registered as 26,5% [6, p.1011-1017; 7, p.143-149; 8, p.273; 12, p.357-359; 15, p. 281-284; 19, p.389-390; 26, p.233-239].

MPS II syndrome among MPS syndromes and their types average frequency equaled 22,9% in European countries. The lowest frequency found for Norway - 4,0% and the highest - 53% in Estonia [17, p. 227-240].

Sanfilippo syndrome spread not evenly throughout world populations, that was confirmed with epidemiology studies. The lowest frequencies of the syndrome were observed 9,0% in Norway and Ireland, and the highest 47,0% and 48,8% were in Netherlands and Poland. In Asian countries the highest frequency was seen in Israel 12,5-23,81% (average 18,6%). The lowest frequency was evaluated for China population as 3,7%. Epidemiology studies showed that Sanfilippo syndrome frequencies were not evenly spread throughout world populations. Epidemiology studies in Western Australia 11 Sanfilippo syndrome patients were identified: 5 patients with Sanfilippo A type, 5 patients with Sanfilippo B type and 1 affected child with Sanfilippo C type. Sanfilippo A type frequency was the same with Sanfilippo B type and equaled 45,5%. 32% of all Sanfilippo syndrome patients from Portugal were patients with MPS IIIB type. It was registered that high frequency of Sanfilippo C was evaluated in Australia 35,5-50,0% (average 42,75%). Frequencies of MPS IIIC syndrome in Australia, Portugal and Netherlands of 100 000 live newborns were respectively 0,07%, 0,12% and 0,21% [6, p.1011-1017; 10, p.205; 14, p.194-195].

Morquio syndrome in European population was spread evenly with 16,67% for both genetic types MPS IVA and MPS IVB. The lowest frequency of syndrome encountered in Sweden - 4,0%, and the highest frequency 32,0% was registered in Northern Ireland [17, p.227-240; 19, p.389-390]. Average frequency 17,69% of this syndrome in Asian continent was observed, the highest frequency was in Israel population (31,25%) and the lowest frequency (9,5%) was found in Southern Korea population [8, p.273]. In American continent Columbia revealed the highest results of syndrome distribution - 60,8%, and the lowest was in the USA - 7,5% [28, p.241]. Morquio syndrome frequencies in Africa and Australia continents distributed as 21,0% and 8,75% [7, p.143-149; 8, p.273; 12, p.357-359; 19, p.389-390; 21, p.387-396].

Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome frequencies among MPS affected were distributed throughout world populations as were registered in the scientific papers: Europe - 6,83% [7, p.143-149; 9, p.11-18; 13, p.108; 14, p.194-195; 16, p.205-210; 19, p.389-390; 21, p.387-396], Africa - 29,5% [24, p.743], Asia - 9,47% [8, p.273; 12, p.357-359; 25, p.231; 27, p.23-29], America - 14,85% [28, p.241] and Australia - 13,0% [18, p.78-95]. The highest frequency was in Africa populations - 28,5% and the lowest - 6,83% in European residents [6, p.1011-1017; 7, p.143-149; 8, p.273; 13, p.108; 14, p. 194-195; 16, p.205-210; 17, p.227-240; 19, p.389-390; 21, p.387-396; 22, p.233-239; 26, p.233-239].

Table 3 presents frequencies of MPS types distribution in world populations through continents and comparison with frequencies of all MPS types identified in Azerbaijan Republic population.

Table 3.

Comparison of MPS frequencies identified in Azerbaijan Republic and world populations

Territory	MPS I	MPS II	MPS III	MPS IV	MPS VI
Europe	Ireland-5%	Norway-4,0%	Norway-9,0%	Sweden-4,0%	Turkey-0,24%
	Sweden-33,9% (17,2%)	Estonia-33,0% (23,9%)	Poland-89,0% (47,5%)	Ireland-32,0% (22,9%)	Estonia-20,0% (2,1%)
Asia	Taiwan-6%	Pakistan-1,1%	China-3,7%	Pakistan-6,67%	Korea-1,4%
	India-88,3% (21,3%)	Japan-55,0% (37,4%)	Israel-18,0% (10,85%)	Israel-31,2% (17,6%)	Malaysia-27,5% (3,2%)
Africa	Tunisia-5%	Arab Emirates-0%	Egypt-9,0%	Egypt- 13,6%	Tunisia-8,0%
	Saudi Arabia-20,1% (20,1%)	Tunisia-8,0% (5,0%)	Tunisia-32,0% (20,5%)	Tunisia-29,6% (21,0%)	Saudi Arabia -46,0% (12,1%)
America	Canada-9,5%	Columbia-5,0%	Columbia-5,0%	USA-7,5%	Mexico-9,95
	Columbia-30,0% (17,3%)	Brazil-33,4% (20,6%)	USA-31,0% (18,0%)	Columbia-60,8% (19,9%)	Brazil-24,5% (11,0%)
Australia	24,1%	13,0%	47,0%	8,8%	8,5%
Average	20,0%	20,0%	28,7%	18,03%	7,4%
Azerbaijan	5,9%	14,7%	20,6%	50,0%	7,7%

Totally, during last 60 years more than 10000 MPS patients in different countries throughout the world were identified and it turned out to be the equal frequencies for Hurler and Hunter syndromes - 20%. The lowest frequency was for Maroteaux-Lamy (MPS VI) syndrome - 7,4%, next was both types of Morquio syndrome (MPS IVA and MPS IVB) - 18,03%. The highest frequency (28,7%) registered for all four types

(A, B, C and D) of Sanfilippo syndrome patients [5, p.65-70; 8, p.273; 17, p.227-240; 25, p.231; 28, p.241].

Differing from mentioned above MPS patients from Azerbaijan Republic were distributed in the population. The lowest frequency of Hurler syndrome (5,9%), next was Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome (7,7%). The highest frequency - around half of all identified MPS syndromes (50%) fall onto Morquio diagnosed patients. MPS IVA/MPS IVB ratio was 16/1. Hurler

and Sanfilippo syndromes' distribution was as 14,7% and 20,6% [1, p.99-105; 2, p.56-58; 3, p.28-36; 4, p.201-209].

CONCLUSIONS

1. For the first time in Azerbaijan Republic population, Mucopolysaccharidoses lysosome storage diseases epidemiology studies were carried out. Totally in 86 economic regions of the Republic, 947 suspicious patients in inherited diseases were tested.

2. All patients suspicious in Mucopolysaccharidoses underwent urine tests for glucosaminoglycans with thin layer chromatography methodique, analyses for corresponding lysosomal enzyme activities, Sanger sequencing and Next Generation Sequencing methodiques to identify and confirm syndrome and their types after medical genetic consultations with every patient and their family members.

3. Five types of Mucopolysaccharidoses: Hurler (MPS I), Hunter (MPS II), Sanfilippo (MPS III), Morquio (MPS IV), Maroteaux-Lamy (MPS VI) identified. 34 patients found to be homozygotes and double heterozygotes, as well as 93 people wer identified as heterozygotes and their inheritance was defined.

4. Comparison of the Mucopolysaccharidoses phenotypic frequencies was given in the table through countries and continents. The lowest frequency was for Hurler syndrome (5,9%), then came Maroteaux-Lamy syndrome (7,7%). The highest frequency was shown for Morquio syndrome - around of all identified MPS syndromes (50%). MPS IVA/MPS IVB ratio was counted as 16/1. Hurler and Sanfilippo syndromes registered frequencies as 14,7% and 20,6%.

5. Obtained practical and scientific results would help professionals to find ways and develop Mucopolysaccharidoses prophylaxis to be used in mutual work with genetically risky families.

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